
MEMORANDUM

TO: Parliamentary Select Committee on Constitutional, Legal and Parliamentary Affairs
FROM: Interfaith Alliance Ghana
SUBJECT: The Promotion of Proper Human Sexual Rights and Ghanaian Family Values Bill, 2021
DATE: 29th September, 2021..

INTRODUCTION

We represent the Interfaith Alliance Ghana. A faith based Organization movement, that has an array of individuals, regardless of their faith background with inclusivity and diversity, working towards the league in religious freedoms in all spheres of the human endeavor.

We would like to submit this memorandum as Ghanaian people of faith religious leaders because, the Promotion of Proper Human Sexual Rights and Ghanaian Family Values Bill, 2021 (the “Bill”), if passed into law, will criminalise lesbians, gays, bisexuals, transgenders and intersex persons (LGBTI) and those who support and care for them. The Bill introduces a wide system of criminalisation which also directly impacts religious leaders and communities. This will provoke hatred and violence and instil fear and mistrust in the Ghanaian society. It will thence undermine the key values that guide us as people of faith.

In light of the dangers of the Bill to Ghanaian citizens and our country as a whole, and the interests of peace and religious tolerance, this memorandum explains why the Bill goes against core principles commonly held across different communities of faith. As people of faith:

- We affirm human dignity and the diversity of human creation made in the image of the Creator.
- We believe the Bill will erode the core values of our faith and damage our nation, to which we all commonly belong.

- We have the responsibility to ensure that our religious traditions are not used to harm.
- The integrity of our faith calls upon us to stand against this Bill.

1 THE DIGNITY AND VALUE OF HUMAN LIFE

Our sacred texts recognise and affirm the dignity of all persons. They teach us that we are all part of the human family of the Creator. Our texts recognise that humankind is created in God's image, and so every human life is valuable. We are bound together as human beings, created in the image of God. As people of faith, we are called to respect and safeguard the dignity and the worthiness of our communities. A law that criminalises a person for who they are is an affront to human dignity and worth. It also undermines the God-given value of the person, as a human being.

2 THEOLOGICAL DIFFERENCES & PERSONAL BELIEFS

The Bill states that: "Among the multi-religious faiths and various traditional and cultural values across the country, an **overwhelming consensus** is established on the position of the nation in **utter rejection** of the practices of and advocacy for the LGBTTQQAAP+ group in conformity with the customary law and **tenets of faith** and respect for public morality" (p3).

The Bill's asserts that religious traditions and sacred texts can be understood and interpreted in a single, absolute and homogenous way. We acknowledge the role of religion in Ghanaian public life. We know too that there are diverse theological perspectives on sexual and gender diversity. Even within different faith groups, there are opposing views. There is no singular view, as the Bill suggests. All our sacred texts are open to different interpretations. We need to guard against those interpretations that are detrimental to human rights and social bonds, and that may be used to justify violence. Faith and religious observance are deeply personal matters. We recognise the position of individuals who believe their faith prevents them from accepting or participating in certain practices. At the same time, we appreciate the real harms caused when the law is used to deprive people of their rights and services simply

because of who they are. An individual is entitled to their personal beliefs, but they are not entitled to harm others on the basis of those beliefs.

Faith is a source of great comfort and hope. Faith can also be an instrument of division. Religious teachings have been used to support the horrors of slavery and colonialism, to deny women the right to vote, to deny black people their full and equal place in society, and to deny minority religious groups equal rights. We have learned from this that it is wrong to use religious teachings to dehumanise and marginalise any group. We know from experience that religious-based condemnation and rejection cause great harm to individuals and society. Religion should never be used to justify unequal treatment, harm and a lack of compassion.

3 **LOVE, COMPASSION AND TOLERANCE**

...there is no scientific basis or genetic rationale for love. There is only the grace of God.

Archbishop Emeritus Desmond Tutu

Humanistic principles lie at the core of every religion. They guide us in our role of safeguarding the inherent dignity of each human being, and in building a society where all people are free from discrimination and violence. Although religious traditions may vary, there are core principles that connect the faiths of the world in a common cause. One such principle is that all among us are children of our Creator. We are all therefore worthy of the love, acceptance and care of our faith and our community. Many faiths also hold dear the value of compassion and the belief in the sacredness of human life (regardless of its condition) as deserving of respect.

The Bill's far-reaching criminalisation of members of society further entrenches stigma and fear. It brings the very real threat of violence. Instead of introducing a law that will weaken religious love, compassion and mutual humanity, we call for tolerant and open dialogue within communities of faith on these sensitive issues. We believe that most people of faith do not hate sexual and gender minorities. However, the Bill will most certainly contribute to hatred and, by

doing so, compromise a basic principle of faith – to treat others as we would want to be treated.

In Clause 3 the Bill compels “**a church, a mosque or other any other [sic] religious or traditional institution or organisation**” to “of this article, the State shall take steps to encourage the integration of appropriate customary values into the fabric of national life.” We acknowledge that there are differing opinions on the social acceptability of sexual and gender diversity. Even within communities of faith, there are varying degrees of openness to even discussing these matters. However, instead of grappling with these questions in a way that is respectful and safe, the passing of the Bill is likely to instil fear and silence about this important aspect of human life. The Bill will demand of us to turn our backs on the realities in our communities. This is contrary to the value of compassion that is central to our faith.

Respect and tolerance are universal values that bind society, ensure peace, and foster dialogue among different kinds of people. All our religious traditions have stories that affirm the value and worth of every person. Even though we ourselves may have different beliefs about certain issues, we hold in common the need for mutual respect and tolerance. But religious intolerance paves a road to discrimination and violence.

4 **SAFE SANCTUARY**

Ghanaian family values as defined in the Bill include “the duty to uphold the cherished societal ideals of selflessness, **communalism** and **good neighbourliness**,**compassion towards the weak and vulnerable**.....that will help establish a free and just Ghanaian society and nation” (Clause 2). It will not be possible for us, as people of faith, to exercise this communalism and good neighbourliness, or to offer compassion to the weak and vulnerable because the Bill criminalises the very activities that would enable us to do so. This is because the Bill also criminalises “**allies**”, defined as “a non-queer **person who supports** or advocates for the queer community” (Clause 2). This affects any individual or organisation that expresses support for LGBTI people or questions the narrow understanding of human sexuality the Bill prescribes. Those who offer support to sexual and gender minorities will face imprisonment. Prohibiting acts or

expressions of sympathy and support for all our neighbours, and for the vulnerable (which include sexual and gender minorities), undermines values that are fundamental to our religious convictions. These provisions will make us criminals in the House of God.

In our sacred texts, God sides with the poor and the marginalised, the hungry and oppressed. Many times in our history, the church has stood with the wronged, the poor, the destitute and powerless against the powerful and against injustice and oppression. Churches, mosques, and other houses of worship are places of safety and refuge, particularly for those who are marginalised. Our religious institutions are open to and serve all people, and the Bill would stop us from doing God's work of continuing to provide safe sanctuary and support to all those in need.

5 VALUING DIVERSE FAMILIES

The Bill alleges that "LGBTQQIAAP+ activities threaten the concept of family and the associated value systems that are central to the social structure of all ethnics groups in Ghana" (p3). Families provide social, psychological, economic and emotional support and security to their members. They are meant to be places of belonging. We question the Bill's narrow interpretation of human sexuality and family values. It overlooks the diversity of Ghanaian society and its family structures. The Bill seeks to address what it sees as a threat to family values. However, criminalising people on the basis of sexuality or gender identity will do exactly that - it will threaten and erode families. It will put mother against child, sister against brother.

Clause 3 "imposes a duty on every citizen and in particular.....**religious institutions and organisations**.....to promote and protect proper human sexual rights and Ghanaian family values as defined in the Bill" (p10). We recognise the rich diversity of Ghanaian society, reflected in the multi-faiths and multi-cultures that make up our nation. We know too that the African family was broken by colonisation. Even today, some of the ideas we have about the African family are based on Eurocentric norms. Our colonial past also erased the many forms of family relationships that have always existed in African societies. Families are diverse. They should be places of mutual care and support. They should be the

place where non-harmful and dignity-affirming relationships thrive, contributing to the well-being of their members and the community at large. Families are especially important for their most vulnerable members.

The Bill condemns LGBTI persons and all who know them, including those who might seek to minister to their plight. This will have a chilling effect on individuals who need access to services and those who are willing to provide such services to marginalised populations. This goes against the bonds of family and community, against the religious message of love, and the African values of common humanity.

6 DO NO HARM

The golden rule of faith is to treat others the way we would want to be treated. This includes those who may seem different from us. When we do this, we are truly living our faith. As people of faith, we recognise the harm caused to our community when we lack vital protections. We need to ensure that no one is ill-treated because of who they are or who they love. Being made a criminal for who you are can only result in unequal treatment, pain and suffering. We seek to call attention to the harms this may cause to the individual, family and the wider society they are a part of. We are concerned that the Bill will become a weapon of harm that will cause hurt and suffering and tear at the very fabric of our society.

We are deeply concerned that the Bill promotes and perpetuates the stigmatisation and discrimination of LGBTI people. The Bill extends criminalisation to, “[a] person who engages in or participates in an activity that **promotes or supports ... sympathy** for an act prohibited under this Act” (Clause 12). This can result in imprisonment of not less than 5 years and up to 10 years. The Bill also prohibits providing “**any form of assistance**” (p12) to those who will be criminalised under the Bill. These provisions undermine our role (as people of faith and as religious leaders) to be able to care for those who are vulnerable.

As people of faith, we have a moral responsibility to provide care and support to our members, irrespective of their sex, sexual orientation or gender identity. This vital care and support will be denied to people by this Bill, and we ourselves

will be criminalised for playing the role we are called on to play because of our faith. As people of faith, we take seriously the call to make visible the loving embrace of God through acts of compassion, hospitality, and care for one another and for those in need. This will be severely undermined should the Bill pass.

The duty to report (Clause 5) in the Bill may, out of fear, cause us to turn against our very own congregations and communities. It will also breed silence and suspicion. No person should be turned away from a community of faith, or by a faith leader. No one should live in fear because of who they are. Failing to protect others from discrimination goes against the principle of treating others the way we want to be treated, and it hurts us all.

7 **SOCIAL WELL-BEING**

Our faith is rooted in values that affirm the life, dignity, and sanctity of all human beings and communities. Criminalising sexual and gender differences in law goes against the social well-being of our fellow citizens, which is paramount to us as people of faith. Clause 5 requires any person witnessing any of the activities prohibited to report those to the police “or in the absence of the police, political leaders, opinion leaders or the customary authorities of the community.” This will foster stigma and intolerance among our constituencies. We are concerned that it will also justify the advocacy of hatred and incitement to violence, and have a life-threatening impact on sexual and gender minorities.

Clause 8 and 9 in the Bill will lead to persons being expelled from their families and places of living because of their real or perceived gender or sexuality. Our religious traditions do not view the existence of sexual or gender differences as a reason to exclude people from family and community life. We also seek a nation in which goodness and love prevail over violence and hate.

In its blanket prohibitions, the Bill will create moral panic over issues of sexual and gender diversity in Ghanaian society. In seeking life-affirming ways to deal with the contentious issue of human sexuality, we should respectfully and compassionately engage with the opportunities for understanding it brings. Faith communities will be weakened if we, as leaders and people of faith, are

called to criminalise those amongst us for who they are. On the other hand, faith communities will be strengthened if we are open and tolerant of difference, even when that difference may be a source of discomfort. It is the religious message of love and compassion that should guide our society in dealing with these issues in the interests of social well-being.

8 **RELIGIOUS FREEDOM**

If a person is gay and seeks God and has good will, who am I to judge him?

Pope Francis

Religious freedom gives us the right to hold our own beliefs as members of society. It does not mean we have the right to impose those beliefs – in the harmful ways contemplated in the Bill – on others, including by discriminating against them for something we might not personally like or support.

In the name of religious freedom, we seek to practice our faith in a way that affirms life, both for us and for others. Our religious values call on us to do this. Valuing religious freedom as we do, we are deeply concerned that the Bill will prevent our ability to minister to *all* those who may seek our ministry. It will also restrict our freedom to practice religion in a way that is inclusive and recognises the dignity of all human beings.

SIGNED

Secretary, Interfaith Alliance Ghana.